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**European Union Proficiency Tests for pesticide residues in fruit and vegetables
from 2009 to 2016: overview of the results and main achievements**

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Abstract

The European Union Reference Laboratory for pesticide residues in Fruits and Vegetables (EURL-FV) is organising, every year since 2004, the European Commission Proficiency Test for multiresidue analysis of pesticides in fruits and vegetables (EUPT-FV), which is directed to all National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) and all Official Laboratories (OfLs) responsible for pesticide residue control in the European Union. This work provides an updated overview of the last eight editions of EUPT-FV (2009-2016), highlighting the main difficulties encountered by the participant laboratories and the key achievements in the field of sample extraction and data dispersion and statistical evaluation. The number of participant laboratories was every year increasing from 151 in 2009 (EUPT-FV11) to 191 in 2016 (EUPT-FV18), and the total number of pesticide residue results reported by the laboratories in this period was close to 18,000. The percentage of acceptable, questionable and unacceptable z scores values assigned in each one of these eight EUPT-FVs has remained very similar with average values of 91.8, 3.5, and 4.7 percent, respectively. The large amount of data results evaluated has led to a strengthening in the use of the 25 percent fit-for-purpose relative standard deviation (FFP-RSD) as well as the use of an internationally accepted 50 percent target expanded measurement uncertainty default value when reporting results for multiresidue analysis of pesticides.

Keywords: Pesticide Residues, EU Proficiency Tests, Multiresidue Methods, Fruits and Vegetables

1. Introduction

The monitoring of pesticide residues in food is relevant for the implementation of Regulations (EC) No 396/2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides (MRLs) and (EC) No 882/2004 on official controls in the framework of an integrated and uniform approach to official controls along the agrifood chain, allowing competent authorities in the Member States to verify compliance with food and feed law. Article 53 of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 on official controls empowers the Commission to recommend coordinated plans organised on an ad hoc basis. The EU multiannual control programme establishes the products to be sampled by the EU Member States and a list of priority substances to be analysed, in order to ensure compliance with MRLs of pesticides and to assess the consumer exposure to pesticide residues in and on food of plant and animal origin. Regulation (EC) N° 882/2004 also establishes EU Reference Laboratories (EURLs) with the aim to ensure high-quality, uniform testing in the EU and support Commission activities on risk management and risk assessment in the area of laboratory analysis.

Proficiency tests by interlaboratory comparison are an effective tool to assess and monitor the quality performance of analytical laboratories (Fernández-Alba, 2004). They are designed principally to enable participant laboratories to detect and remedy shortcomings in their procedures (Thompson, Ellison, & Wood, 2006; International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2010). Participation in proficiency tests is part of the external quality assessment of the laboratory, and it is a requirement in order to be accredited under ISO/IEC 17025:2005 (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2005). Within this context, the EURL for pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables (EURL-FV) annually organises EU-proficiency tests (EUPTs) on behalf of the European Commission to evaluate the competency of the EU National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) and EU

Official Laboratories (OfLs) for analysing pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables. For those laboratories undertaking pesticide residue analyses within the frame of national and EU official controls, participation in EUPTs is mandatory. Laboratories from the European Free Trade Association (EFTA), as well as laboratories from non-EU/EFTA countries can also participate after approval by DG SANTE (Directorate General for Health and Food Safety-European Commission). In 1996, the National Food Administration in Uppsala (Sweden) in cooperation with the University of Almería (Spain) started organising the EUPTs-FV. Since 2004, the EURL-FV has organised them on behalf of the European Commission, DG SANTE. In that 20-year period (1996-2016), 18 editions have been performed in 17 different fruit and vegetable commodities, and using a total of 113 different pesticides, which has resulted in the generation of more than 30600 pesticide residue results using multiresidue methods (European Union Reference Laboratory for Residues of Pesticides in Fruits and Vegetables-EURL-FV) (the network of EU OfLs is comprised of around 170 routine laboratories analysing fruits and vegetables using multiresidue methods). Detailed information on the history, organization and protocols of the EUPTs-FV was published by Medina-Pastor *et al.* (Medina-Pastor, Fernández-Alba, Andersson, & Rodríguez-Torreblanca, 2010), together with the evaluation of the results from EUPT-FV01 to EUPT-FV10. A summary of the matrices, number of participants, number of possible pesticides and number of pesticides evaluated in the test item of the last eight EUPTs-FV is presented in Table 1. As can be observed in the table, participation in these EUPTs has increased over the years, being the number of participants 25 percent higher in EUPT-FV18 than in EUPT-FV11. This can be explained by the growing increase of OfLs due to the incorporation of new Member States into the EU, to the growth of the laboratory networks, and the increment of non-EU/EFTA participants as a result of the big impact of the international trade between EU and other

external countries. In the last eight years, the percentage of non-EU/EFTA participants has ranged between 5 and 10 percent.

The number of pesticides in the Pesticide Target List (list of possible pesticides in the test item) has also increased in the last eight-year period, from 128 compounds in EUPT-FV11 to 190 in EUPT-FV18, in parallel with the growth of the number of pesticides included in the EU multiannual control programme.

From 2014 onwards, the EUPTs-FV have been organised under ISO/IEC 17043 accreditation (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2010), which is the International Standard that specifies general requirements for the competence of providers of proficiency testing schemes and for the development and operation of proficiency testing schemes. Before that, all EUPTs-FV were performed according to the specifications of the International Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation Guideline (International Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation, 2000), of ISO/IEC 17043 (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2010) and ISO Guide 43 (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 1999). Based on the aforementioned standards, the organisation of the EUPTs-FV follows the procedures established in both the EUPT-General Protocol and the corresponding EUPT-Specific Protocol, drafted and updated by the EUPT-Scientific Committee. That committee also sets out the Pesticide Target List for each round, together with the Minimum Required Reporting Levels (MRRLs) for each pesticide (the level that laboratories are expected to attain using their analytical methods).

This work aims to provide an updated overview of the last eight years of EUPTs in fruits and vegetables, highlighting the main difficulties encountered by the participant laboratories and the key achievements in the field of sample extraction and data dispersion and statistical evaluation.

2. Overview of the Results

2.1 Estimation of the Assigned Value and data variability

Different approaches can be followed to calculate the assigned value (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2010; International Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation, 2000; Thompson, Mertens, Kessler, & Fearn, 1993). In the case of EUPTs-FV, it is the consensus value (taking into account the results reported by EU and EFTA countries' laboratories only) that derives directly from the reported results. From EUPT-FV17 onwards, and in order to minimise the influence of outlying results on the statistical evaluation, the assigned value has been estimated using robust estimate of the participant's mean, as described in Annex C of ISO 13528:2015 (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2015), where the robust mean according to algorithm A is defined. The uncertainty of the assigned values $u(x_{pt})$ is also calculated according to ISO 13528:2015 as

$$u(x_{pt}) = 1.25 \times \frac{s^*}{\sqrt{p}}$$

where s^* is the robust standard deviation and p is the number of results. If $u(x_{pt}) < 0.3 \sigma_{pt}$ then the uncertainty of the assigned value may be considered to be negligible and wouldn't need to be included in the interpretation of the results of the round of proficiency testing (being σ_{pt} the standard deviation for proficiency assessment).

Data variability has been calculated in various ways in the different EUPTs-FV. Since EUPT-FV04, the FFP- σ_{pt} has been calculated using a fit for purpose approach with a fixed relative standard deviation (FFP-RSD) of 25 percent as follows: FFP- $\sigma_{pt} = 0.25 \times x_{pt}$. The

effectiveness of the use of 25 percent as FFP-RSD has been supported by the results obtained in different proficiency tests (Alder, Korth, Patey, Van Der Schee, & Schoeneweiss, 2001; Medina-Pastor, Fernández-Alba, et al., 2010; Medina-Pastor, et al., 2011) and has also been implemented in guidelines for estimation of the uncertainty of the results such as the CODEX Guidelines ("Codex Alimentarius - CAC/GL 59: Guidelines on Estimation of Uncertainty of Results").

For informative purposes, data variability in terms of dispersion of results has also been calculated in the EUPTs-FV applying robust statistics, by calculation of the standard deviations using the robust dispersion, Qn-RSD (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2010; Fernández-Alba, 2004; Müller & Uhlig, 2001) (up to EUPT-FV16) or the robust relative standard deviation CV* (EUPT-FV17 and EUPT-FV18) following Algorithm A in Annex C of ISO 13528:2015. The representation of the dispersion of the EU proficiency tests results for each pesticide in the last eight years reveals the improvement of the participant laboratories, as it has decreased with the years independently of the concentration levels (Figure 1). As can be observed in the figure, there is a trend towards improvement among European laboratories, being 20 percent the average RSD of the last five EUPTs-FV. This figure bolsters the use of the 25 percent FFP-RSD as well as of the internationally accepted 50 percent target expanded measurement uncertainty for multiresidue analysis of pesticides (Codex Alimentarius, 2011; Medina-Pastor, et al., 2011)

2.2 False Positives and Negatives

False positives are results of pesticides from the Target Pesticide List that are reported at, or above, their respective MRRL although they were not used in the preparation of the test material and not detected by the overwhelming majority of participants nor by the Organiser. Results reported that were lower than the MRRL were disregarded, and

therefore not considered to be false positives. Table 2 gathers the number of false positive results reported in the last eight EUPTs-FV. The average number of false positives is 12, with a minimum of three (EUPT-FV16) and a maximum of 19 in EUPT-FV12, which evidences the uneven distribution between them. When the technique of analysis is considered, the differences between false positive results obtained by gas chromatography (GC) or by liquid chromatography (LC) are remarkable (average of eight false positives by GC and four by LC). This can be explained by the significant higher number of classical detectors coupled to GC than to LC, which in most of the cases was coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (triple quadrupole analysers).

False negatives are results for pesticides reported by the laboratories as 'analysed' but without reporting numerical values, although they were used by the Organiser to treat the test item and detected by the Organiser as well as the majority of the participants that had targeted those specific pesticides at or above the respective MRRLs. The percentage of false negatives per maximum number of possible determinations (assuming that every participant had reported all the pesticides present in the test item) shows a declining trend in the last eight EUPTs-FV, with an average value of 1.3 percent (see Table 3). This reduction in the percentage of false negatives over the years is related to the progressive inclusion by the participant laboratories of LC-MS/MS systems, but also to the presence of new and more sensitive instrumentation.

2.3 z score values obtained

To assess the performance of the participating laboratories for individual pesticides, z scores have been calculated in all the EUPTs-FV using the following formula:

$$z_i = \frac{(x_i - x_{pt})}{FFP - \sigma_{pt}}$$

where x_i is the value reported by the laboratory, x_{pt} is the assigned value, and $FFP-\sigma_{pt}$ is the standard deviation using fit for purpose approach, that is, 25 percent of FFP-RSD multiplied by the assigned value.

z scores are interpreted in the following way, as is set in ISO/IEC 17043 (International Organization for Standardization-ISO, 2010):

$ z \leq 2.0$	Acceptable
$2.0 < z < 3.0$	Questionable
$ z \geq 3.0$	Unacceptable

For results considered as false negatives, z scores have been calculated using the MRRL or the laboratory's reporting limit (RL) if the $RL < MRRL$. For false positive results no z score has been calculated. In the last eight years the percentage of acceptable, questionable and unacceptable z scores has remained very similar (Table 4) (average value of acceptable z scores 91.8 percent, average of value of questionable results 3.5 percent and average percentage of unacceptable z scores 4.7 percent), with a few exceptions as a result of the selection of "difficult matrices" for the test item. That was the case of EUPT-FV12 (leek), with the highest percentage of unacceptable z scores (7.1 percent) and EUPT-FV13 (mandarin), with the lowest percentage of acceptable z scores (89.0 percent)

2.4 Combined z scores

A defining characteristic of EUPTs-FV is the relatively large number of pesticides included in the test item, given that one of their purposes is to evaluate the capacity of the EU OfLs to report results obtained by multiresidue methods. The application of the z scores to those multiresidue methods, where each laboratory obtains a large number of

single z scores, makes it difficult to get a clear evaluation of the overall laboratory assessment (Medina-Pastor, Mezcua, Rodríguez-Torreblanca, & Fernández-Alba, 2010). Since EUPT-FV14, the evaluation of the overall performance of laboratories with positive detection of at least 90 percent of the total number of pesticides present in the test material and which reported no false positives - namely Category A, has been accomplished using the Average of the Squared z score (AZ^2) (Medina-Pastor, Mezcua, Rodríguez-Torreblanca, & Fernández-Alba, 2010). The AZ^2 is calculated as follows:

$$AZ^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n z_i^2}{n}$$

Where n is the number of z scores to be considered in the calculation. For this calculation, z scores higher than 5 will be set as 5. Based on the AZ^2 achieved, the laboratories are classified as follows:

$AZ^2 \leq 2.0$	Good
$2.0 < AZ^2 < 3.0$	Satisfactory
$AZ^2 \geq 3.0$	Unsatisfactory

Traditionally, combined z score results for laboratories in Category A have been plotted in bar charts. Figure 2 shows the first and the last graph of the combined z score results in the last eight year-period. The test item was based on cauliflower and spinach, respectively. Both of them belong to the group of commodities of high water content (SANTE 11945/2015), although each one of them presents specific difficulties, such as the presence of sulphur compounds in the case of the cauliflower, and chlorophyll in the spinach. Despite that fact, the results along the years have improved, being 79 percent the percentage of “good” combined z scores in EUPT-FV11 and 88 percent in EUPT-FV18, highlighting the positive evolution of the EU OfLs.

2.5 Classification of the laboratories-Category A and B

With the introduction of the overall laboratory assessment by means of the combined z scores, the EUPT Scientific Committee together with DG SANTE decided to classify the laboratories into two categories, A and B, based on the scope of the participants. Laboratories in Category A were those that reported at least 90 percent of the pesticides present in the test item and did not report any false positive result. The rest of participants were classified in Category B. The percentage of laboratories in Category A has increased with the years, from 51 percent in EUPT-FV11 to 68 percent in EUPT-FV17 (see Figure 3). But to understand the real evolution of those laboratories it is important to consider the number of pesticides included in the Pesticide Target List, as the more pesticides in the list, the more difficult for the laboratories to be in Category A. Over the same period of time, the number of pesticides in the Target List has increased approximately 40 percent (from 128 to 183 pesticides, see Table 1), which emphasizes the progress made by laboratories in Category A. However, the number of laboratories that cannot cover the whole scope proposed in the EUPT is still big, considering that the scope of the EUPT is in line with the scope of the EU monitoring program. This implies that there is a substantial number of laboratories that can only produce an incomplete evaluation of the analysed samples. Table 3 shows the percentage of not analysed pesticides per maximum number of possible determinations, which presents an average value of 18 percent from the past eight years. In order to encourage the laboratories to enlarge their scope, category A/B classification was modified in EUPT-FV18, where an additional requirement was added; Laboratories that were able to analyse at least 90 percent of the compulsory pesticides in the Target Pesticides List, had correctly detected and quantified a sufficiently high percentage of the pesticides present in the Test Item (at least 90 percent) and reported no false positives demonstrated ‘sufficient scope’ and therefore were classified into Category A. This more stringent categorisation meets the requirements of DG SANTE as

to the enlargement of the scope of analysis of EU OfLs. Predictably, the introduction of the new requirement had an impact in the percentage of laboratories in Category A hampering its growth. However, the figure (57 percent participants in Category A in EUPT-FV18) is similar to the results of the previous EUPTs-FV. As regards the new requirement, being able to analyse at least 90 percent of the compulsory pesticides in the Target Pesticides List, it is met by 62 percent of the EU/EFTA participants, whilst 11 percent of the OfLs analyse less than 50 percent of the scope.

2.6 Laboratory “Triple-A” rating approach

The classification above considers two groups or categories (A and B) depending on the number of detections reported by the laboratory, without considering the accuracy of the reported results; it is to say, without taking into account the z scores values assigned to the reported results. Thus, this classification does not give clear information on the overall quality of the laboratories, and may create some confusion at the time of identifying competent and non-competent laboratories. Valverde *et al.* (Valverde, Fernández-Alba, Ferrer, & Aguilera, 2016) defined a new three-dimensional (XYZ) classification, with three categories (A, B or C) within each dimension, that is proposed to evaluate performance-underperformance of laboratories participating in the EUPT-FV. According to this proposal, laboratories would be evaluated taking into account the number of detected pesticides (dimension X: scope), the number of acceptable z-scores (dimension Y: performance), and the number of false positives (dimension Z: false positives). The borderline criteria for establishing categories A, B and C in scope (X) and performance (Y) are 90 percent and 50 percent of either the total number of pesticides present in the tests item or the total number of z-scores assigned to the laboratory, but those laboratories classified as C in scope can only be classified as B or C in performance, the borderline criteria being in this case 90 percent. Finally, laboratories are classified as A, B or C into

the third dimension when they report none, one, or more than one false positive, respectively. This new approach has not been implemented to the EUPTs, as it is still under consideration. In this work the new classification has been applied to the last four EUPTs-FV in order to compare the results with the current two-dimensional categorisation (A or B). For this comparison, EU competent laboratories in the two-dimensional categorisation were those classified in Category A with a combined z score value < 3 (good or satisfactory). In the Triple-A rating approach, competent laboratories were those classified as AAA (those reporting ≥ 90 percent of the pesticides of the test item, with ≥ 90 percent of acceptable z scores and not reporting any false positive result). Figure 4 shows the comparison of laboratories in category A and laboratories in category AAA and ABA within the Triple-A approach for EUPT-FV14 to EUPT-FV18. Except in the case of EUPT-FV18, where a new factor was included for the classification of laboratories into category A or B, the percentage of laboratories in Category A is equivalent to the sum of laboratories classified as AAA and ABA. If the comparison is made between AAA laboratories and laboratories in category A with $AZ^2 < 3$, the percentages are very similar, although always slightly lower in the case of the Triple-A approach. This can be explained because the current classification has more flexible criteria. The advantage of the new Triple-A approach is that it allows further classification of those laboratories included in the current category B, giving more information about the performance of those laboratories. The Triple-A approach was applied to all participant laboratories in EUPT-FV18. It can be noted in Figure 5 that category AAA has the highest percentage (X percent). The rest of laboratories are distributed in percentages below 15 percent. Laboratories classified in Category B in the two-dimensional classification are classified into nine categories within the new approach, which allows to differentiate those laboratories reporting false positive results (AAB,

BAB, CCB and CCC) and give more information than the two-dimensional approach. Furthermore, this new classification does not establish unrealistic differences between laboratories where small differences (for example, $AZ^2=0.8$ and $AZ^2=1.1$) in their average of z score imply moving from good to satisfactory results.

2.7 Follow-up of specific pesticides through different EUPTs-FV

The number of pesticides evaluated in the EUPTs-FV test items has fluctuated over time, with an average value of 17 and a total number of 138 pesticides in the last eight years. The presence of a specific pesticide in different rounds provides a comprehensive review of how the participant laboratories are progressing. One example is the case of spirodiclofen. That pesticide was introduced new in the pesticide target list in EUPT-FV14, and it was also included in the test item (pear). The percentage of laboratories that reported results was quite low, compared to the other pesticides in the test item: 58 percent. The following year, spirodiclofen was used again for the preparation of the test item (potato), and the percentage of reported results increased to 66 percent. Moreover, the number of false negative results decreased from three in EUPT-FV14 to one in EUPT-FV15, and the classification of the z scores improved the second year, with 4 percent of unacceptable z scores in EUPT-FV15 versus 9 percent in EUPT-FV14.

3. Analytical difficulties encountered by the participants

3.1 Influence of the extraction method in the results

Multiresidue extraction methods for pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables in the EU are based mainly on three extraction solvents: acetonitrile (e.g. QuEChERS (M. Anastassiades, Lehotay, Štajnbaher, & Schenck, 2003; Lehotay, Maštovská, & Lightfield, 2005; "UNE-EN 15662:2009 Foods of plant origin - Determination of pesticide residues

using GC-MS and/or LC-MS/MS following acetonitrile extraction/partitioning and clean-up by dispersive SPE - QuEChERS-method," 2009), ethyl acetate (e.g. SweEt (Pihlström, Blomkvist, Friman, Pagard, & Österdahl, 2007) and acetone (e.g. Dutch mini-Luke (Hiemstra & de Kok, 2007)). In EUPT-FV11, the percentage of reported results that used acetonitrile as extraction solvent was 48 percent (Figure 6), whereas 28 percent of the results were obtained with ethyl acetate based methods, and 24 percent used acetone for the extraction of pesticides. With the years, the use of acetonitrile as extraction solvent has increased, with 83 percent of the results in EUPT-FV18. In the same round, 9 percent of the results were obtained using acetone, and 7 percent used ethyl acetate as extraction solvent. In the case of QuEChERS, approximately 30 percent of the results do not use primary secondary amine (PSA) sorbent in the clean-up step, as it is not always necessary and it can interact with acidic pesticides causing low recoveries, or give undesirable hydrolysis reactions in some cases.

However, the different distribution of number of results per extraction method is not related with the quality of the results, as is evidenced in Figure 7 and Figure 8. In Figure 7, the percentage of acceptable, questionable and unacceptable z scores was calculated for EUPT-FV12 to EUPT-FV18 by grouping the results by extraction solvent applied. The percentage of acceptable z scores is approximately 90 percent for all the EUPTs evaluated and using the three different extraction methods. Questionable and unacceptable z scores remain at around 5 percent each in all the studied cases.

Figure 8 presents the average data dispersion of the last four EUPT-FV results (expressed as CV (percent)) by extraction solvent. In general, the dispersion of the results in the last four years has an average value of 20 percent, with non-significant differences between the extraction methods. This value is very similar to the average value considering all the results. In EUPT-FV17 and EUPT-FV18, the dispersions of the results using ethyl acetate

for the extraction were higher than with the other solvents studied, but in those cases the CV was calculated with an average population of 12 results per pesticide, much lower than in the case of acetonitrile, with an average population of 110 results per pesticide. Figures 7 and 8 bring to light that, in general, for multiresidue methods the choice of the extraction method does not have a big impact in the quality of the results. However, special attention has to be paid to specific pesticide-matrix combinations, as the example below demonstrates.

3.1.1 Specific case: Chlorothalonil in leek (EUPT-FV12)

An illustrative example on how for specific pesticide-matrix combinations the extraction method can affect the results is the one of chlorothalonil in leek (EUPT-FV12). One hundred and fourteen participants indicated that they had analysed it, but only less than half of them, 53, reported results (assigned value 0.216 mg/kg). The remaining 61 participants (53 percent) had false negative results for chlorothalonil, which is a value extremely high in comparison with the usual percentage of false negatives, as discussed in section 2.2. The investigation of the conditions of analysis of the different participants revealed that most of the laboratories that used extraction methods based on acetonitrile (e.g. QuEChERS) could not detect chlorothalonil in the leek test item (false negative results). The best results reported in this proficiency test were achieved by those participant laboratories that used acetone for solvent extraction. Figure 9 shows the z score values for chlorothalonil highlighting with different colours the different solvents used during the extraction method. Chlorothalonil normally does not cause extraction problems, but when it is present in matrices that contain sulphur atoms, such as leek, the extraction process becomes difficult. This is a consequence of the binding of

chlorothalonil to the sulphur derivative groups present in those commodities, which can trap the pesticide, thereby hindering its extraction (Belmonte Valles, et al., 2012)

In addition, chlorothalonil is susceptible to hydrolysis at high pH (>9) and is very sensitive to temperature changes (Szalkowski & Stallard, 1977). The choice of extraction solvent can be decisive in the extraction efficiency of the analytical method. This makes it clear that in occasions, certain pesticide-matrix combinations can be problematic when analysed with specific multiresidue extraction methods.

3.2 Influence of the analytical standard solutions in the results

Analytical standard solutions play an essential role in the analysis of pesticide residues. In some cases, questionable and unacceptable results in proficiency tests are closely related to an inadequate quantification as a result of a problem with the standard solutions. Among the possible causes of error, one is the low stability of certain compounds, as is the case of benomyl and thiophanate methyl, which degrade into carbendazim (Dorweiler, Gurav, Walbridge, Ghatge, & Savant, 2016; Michelangelo Anastassiades & Schwack, 1998) When those three compounds were present in the same mix of analytical standards and the standard is used to quantify carbendazim, there is underestimation of the concentration of carbendazim.

A second source of error would be the opposite situation: the low solubility of certain pesticides in organic solvents, which would lead to an overestimation of the concentration.

The presence of isomers in the same analytical standard might also lead to errors in quantification. This has been observed in the EU proficiency tests in which spinosad was included in the test item. This pesticide consists on a mixture of two isomers: spinosyn A and spinosyn D, in different proportions that are in some cases unknown. As those two

compounds are different and have different retention times, laboratories that quantify each one of the isomers with the corresponding isomer of the analytical standard without considering the proportion of each of the isomers in the mix are overestimating the concentration of spinosad in the test item. This has been observed in EUPT-FV13, EUPT-FV16 and EUPT-FV17, where in the three cases the graphical representation of the z scores for spinosad showed a high number of z scores ≥ 3 , thus indicating an overestimation of the results.

3.2.1 Specific case: Carbendazim in EUPT-FV12, EUPT-FV13 and EUPT-FV17

In the history of the EU proficiency tests, carbendazim has been used in three occasions for the preparation of the test item: EUPT-FV12 (leek), EUPT-FV13 (mandarin) and EUPT-FV17 (broccoli). In the three of them, the percentage of acceptable z scores was one of the lower ones (average of 85 percent). This low performance of carbendazim could be attributed to stability issues of the benzimidazole fungicides during the sample extraction procedure (Guo, et al., 2010). However, in the same study it was indicated that carbendazim degradation to 2-amino benzimidazole happens very slowly in strong alkaline conditions (pH >11), which is not the case of most of the multiresidue methods. A further study of the z score graphs revealed that in the three proficiency tests evaluated, carbendazim z score graphs presented a significant number of z scores > 3, which implies an overestimation of the concentration (Figure 10). Considering the low solubility of carbendazim in organic solvents (e.g. 0.135 g/l in ethyl acetate, <0.01 g/l in cyclohexane (*The Pesticide Manual, seventeenth edition, 2015*)) it seems reasonable to suspect that the overestimation is caused by the use of incorrectly dissolved analytical standards solutions for quantification of carbendazim in the proficiency tests samples.

3.3 Influence of the chromatographic technique in the results

The choice of the most appropriate determination technique is one of the most important decisions in pesticide residue analysis. Although some compounds can only be analysed by GC or LC, for most of the pesticides both techniques can be applied for their analysis (Alder, Greulich, Kempe, & Vieth, 2006). However, in some occasions the results differ significantly when a certain pesticide is analysed by GC or by LC. An example of this is given hereunder.

3.3.1 Specific case: Monocrotophos in EUPT-FV07 and EUPT-FV11

In EUPT-FV07 (grapes) monocrotophos presented two different distributions depending on the determination technique used (Medina-Pastor, Fernández-Alba, et al., 2010). Further examination of the information provided by the participants revealed that most of the results with negative z scores employed gas chromatography whilst most of the positive z score results used liquid chromatography (Figure 11). The polarity of monocrotophos makes the analysis by GC problematic, as peak tailing has a negative impact on quantification (Banerjee, Dasgupta, & Utture, 2012). In EUPT-FV11 monocrotophos was also used to prepare the test item (cauliflower). Fig.11 shows the corresponding z score graph where the z scores were similar for the GC results. In the case of LC, more results presented negative z scores than in EUPT-FV07, probably due to the suppression caused by the characteristic nature of the matrix (cauliflower).

4. Conclusions

Proficiency tests are a valuable tool to follow the different stages of the analytical process. The collection of information during the past eight years (EUPT-FV11 to EUPT-FV18) involving all EU OfLs for pesticide residue control has generated vast amounts of data

and has led to very valuable achievements in areas such as test sample preparation, data dispersion and statistical evaluation; as well as giving an overview as to the effectiveness of proficiency tests as an important tool in the development of quality control results in laboratories involved in food control. Over the years, the number of compounds included in the Pesticide Target List has increased, as well as the number of participant laboratories. The dispersion of the results submitted by the laboratories has been evaluated with the robust dispersion, which has decreased with the years independently of the concentration levels, highlighting the improvement of the participant laboratories. Another achievement in data dispersion is that the big amount of data results has led to a strengthening in the use of the 25 percent fit-for-purpose relative standard deviation (FFP-RSD) as well as the use of an internationally accepted 50 percent target expanded measurement uncertainty for multiresidue analysis of pesticides. Specific difficulties represent relevant information for the laboratories in order to avoid mistakes that can be produced in routine in steps such as sample preparation, sample extraction and analysis, affecting seriously the performance of the laboratory.

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Figure 2. Evolution of the combined z score results from EUPT-FV11 to EUPT-FV18.

Figure 3. Classification of participant laboratories into Category A/B from EUPT-FV11 to EUPT-FV18.

Figure 4. Comparison of Laboratories in Category A (with AZ2<3 in blue and AZ2>3 in grey) and Laboratories in Category AAA (dark blue) and ABA (dark blue stripes) within the Triple-A approach for EUPT-FV14 to EUPT-FV18.

Figure 5. Triple-A approach categories for EUPT-FV18.

Figure 6. Evolution of the extraction solvents from EUPT-FV11 to EUPT-FV18.

Figure 7. Classification of z scores according to different extraction solvents.

Figure 8. Average data dispersion of the last four EUPTs-FV results (expressed as CV (percent)) calculated by extraction solvent.

Figure 9. Graphical representation of z scores for chlorothalonil results in EUPT-FV12. The colours of the bars represent the different solvents used in the extraction process.

Figure 10. Graphical representation of z scores for carbendazim results in a) EUPT-FV12 (leek), b) EUPT-FV13 (mandarin), and c) EUPT-FV17 (broccoli).

Figure 11. Graphical representation of z scores for monocrotophos results in EUPT-FV07 (grapes) and EUPT-FV11 (cauliflower).

Table 1. General information of the EUPTs-FV organized during the period 2009-2016

EUPT Number	Year	Matrices	Number of Participating Labs.	Number of possible pesticides	Number of pesticides evaluated in the test item
FV-11	2009	Cauliflower	151	128	21
FV-12	2010	Leek	153	144	17
FV-13	2011	Mandarin	154	144	19
FV-14	2012	Pear	167	175	17
FV-15	2013	Potato	175	175	18
FV-16	2014	Pepper	183	175	22
FV-17	2015	Broccoli	185	183	11
FV-18	2016	Spinach	191	190	12

Table 2. Number of false positive results in the last eight EUPTs-FV and the determination technique used to report them.

EUPT Number	Number of False Positives	Number of False Positives by Gas Chromatography	Number of False Positives by Liquid Chromatography
FV-11	11	6	5
FV-12	19	14	5
FV-13	9	8	1
FV-14	17	11	6
FV-15	12	6	5
FV-16	3	2	1
FV-17	11	8	3
FV-18	13	11	2

Table 3. Number of false negative results and non-analysed (NA) pesticides in the last eight EUPTs-FV

EUPT No.	Number of NA Pesticides	Maximum number of Possible Determinations	% of NA per maximum number of possible determinations	Number of Pesticides in Target List	Number of Pesticides Present	Number of False Negatives	% of False Negatives per maximum number of possible determinations
FV-11	691	3171	22	128	21	44	1.4
FV-12	569	2601	22	144	17	62	2.4
FV-13	697	2926	24	144	19	43	1.5
FV-14	515	2839	18	175	17	37	1.3
FV-15	566	3150	18	175	18	33	1.0
FV-16	610	4026	15	175	22	40	1.0
FV-17	236	2035	12	183	11	12	0.6
FV-18	345	2292	15	190	12	34	1.5

Table 4. Classification of z scores from EUPT-FV11 to EUPT-FV18.

EUPT No.	% Acceptable	% Questionable	% Unacceptable
FV-11	90.1	5.1	4.8
FV-12	90.9	2.0	7.1
FV-13	89.0	5.0	6.0
FV-14	92.4	3.0	4.6
FV-15	93.4	3.4	3.2
FV-16	92.9	3.3	3.8
FV-17	92.6	3.3	4.1
FV-18	93.2	2.8	4.0